

Inverse identification of a 3D anisotropic yield function through an information-rich tensile test and multi-sDIC

S. Coppieters^{1*}, Y. Zhang¹, N. Vancraeynest¹, A. Lambrugh¹ and S. Cooreman²

¹Department of Materials Engineering, KU Leuven Ghent Campus.

²ArcelorMittal Global R&D Gent / OCAS NV

*sam.coppieters@kuleuven.be

Abstract. In the case of thick high strength steels, 3D anisotropic yield criteria are required to accurately capture the plastic material response. Material testing 2.0 aims at extracting material behaviour from an information-rich mechanical experiment with aid of inverse methods and full-field measuring techniques. In this context, inverse identification of 3D anisotropy through a single experiment is particularly challenging because of the large amount of anisotropy parameters. The difficulty lies in the specimen design that ideally ensures a simultaneous activation of all sought anisotropy parameters with sufficient sensitivity towards the observed strain field. In this contribution, we scrutinize the effectiveness of a specimen designed by shape optimization to inversely identify a 3D anisotropic yield function. This is done via a so-called Digital Virtual Twin (DVT) mimicking the actual measurement including the Digital Image Correlation (DIC). Given that the synthetic data is generated with a known material model used by the FE model, the identification accuracy of the Finite Element Model Updating (FEMU) approach can be objectively assessed. The novelty here is that the synthetic data consists of the data captured by two stereo-DIC (sDIC) systems. Moreover, the FEMU approach accounts for the multi-sDIC data sets. The DVT-results show that the adopted specimen design enables to simultaneously identify the sought anisotropy parameters. The proposed methodology is experimentally validated on S700MC steel with a thickness of 12 mm.

Keywords: F3D anisotropic yield function; Material Testing 2.0; High Strength Steels; Inverse Methods.

Introduction

Denys et al. [1] numerically showed that a double perforated specimen (see left panel Figure 1) enables to inversely identify the shear anisotropy parameter (Figure 1, right panel, see parameter L) using FEMU and two sDIC systems. The key point for successful identification is the side hole in the specimen activating the sought out-of-plane shear anisotropy parameter. However, Denys et al. [2] reported that this was only possible by sequential inverse identification. In a first stage of the inverse identification, the in-plane anisotropy parameters are sought while the out-of-plane shear anisotropy parameters are fixed to their isotropic value. In the next identification phase, the found in-plane anisotropy parameters are used as an initial guess for simultaneously identifying all anisotropy parameters using the front and the side data. The evolution of the

parameter identification is shown in the right panel of Figure 1. It can be inferred that this two-step approach enables to accurately identify all sought anisotropy parameters.

Fig. 1. Double perforated tensile specimen used for sequential inverse identification anisotropy parameters (3D Hill48). After [2].

Unfortunately, the required two-step approach basically indicated that the identification is not robust. Given that these results were obtained using synthetic DIC data generated by an FE model, and, and thus ignoring the experimental noise, this non-robustness might be caused by a non-uniqueness issue as reported by Zhang et al. [3]. The latter can also be enhanced by a lack of parameter sensitivity. In addition, the small size of the side hole causes a strong localized deformation. In general, the Area of Interest (AOI) is much larger and consists of a large amount of material points subjected to homogeneous stress states and small plastic strains. As such, the information-rich data points are often outnumbered, and, consequently, do not contribute to the identification of the sought parameters. This phenomenon biases the inverse identification. Hence, an information-rich experiment in this context, has the following characteristics: i) inhomogeneous plastic deformation, ii) the deformation is not highly localized and iii) sufficiently large plastic strains are probed. When complying with these characteristics, it is also likely that DIC can reliably capture the generated displacement fields. Figure 2 shows a tensile specimen that was derived via shape optimization [4]. The same approach as Denys et al. [1, 2] was followed to objectively assess the identifiability through multi stereo-DIC measurements. As opposed to the work of Denys et al., the results in Figure 2 show that all anisotropy parameters can be simultaneously identified. Accurate results were obtained after two iterations; see the right panel of Figure 2. This confirms that all anisotropy parameters, including the shear anisotropy parameters (L and M) are sufficiently strong activated. An important caveat is that the results shown in Figure 1 and Figure 2 are merely verification results. Indeed, the results

are obtained with data (i.e. the strain fields) generated by a FE model with known anisotropy parameters. As such, experimental noise and post-processing effects (e.g. DIC algorithm) are excluded from the analysis. Consequently, such an analysis merely verifies the FEMU approach, yet cannot guarantee the practical identifiability. In other words, when this procedure is applied in practice, other factors come into play that might bias the conclusions drawn based on the virtual experiment. To this end, it is mandatory to include the metrological aspects of DIC in the Digital Virtual Twin (DVT) of the experiment. For the inverse problem at hand, we must account for two stereo-DIC setups in the DVT. The aim of this paper is to present a generic approach to do so. In the second part of the paper, we embark on assessing the identification quality when targeting 3D anisotropy using the specimen shown in Figure 2. To this end, the DVT is used to synthetically generate DIC data. Finally, the last part of the paper discusses the experimental validation of the proposed methodology.

Fig. 2. Complex mechanical test for the inverse identification of a 3D anisotropic yield function. (a) Specimen (b-c) and verification analysis of the FEMU approach.

1 Digital Virtual Twin of the information-rich tensile test

More than a decade ago, the DVT-concept to evaluate the accuracy of DIC was presented by Lava et al.[5]. The technology for realistically deforming a speckle pattern using a FE model turned out to be very useful for evaluating the complete identification chain. Indeed, prior to directly resorting to actual experiments, we can mimic the complete experiment in advance. This offers the possibility to optimize the experimental conditions, but also to understand potential artefacts introduced by numerical computations or identification strategies. The key principles of the image deformation presented in [5] are now commercially available in MatchID3D via the FEDEF module. This module is used to synthetically deform a real speckle pattern (shown in Figure 3) based on a FE simulation of the experiment (see Figure 2) employing the ground truth material model. The input for the FEDEF module is extracted from the simulation, i.e.: the finite elements mesh and the nodal displacements within the AOI. Furthermore, a speckle pattern, the calibration parameters of the stereo-DIC set up and the level of image noise (obtained from still images using the DIC setup). The image deformation process results in a set of deformed images for camera 0 and camera 1. Those images can then be processed by MatchID 3D to retrieve the displacement fields as shown in

Figure 3. The novelty here is that the synthetic data consists of full-field 3D data, which is clearly shown by the side surface in Figure 3(b). For each load step, two image pairs (camera 0 and camera 1) are generated by the FEDEF module. In this paper, the thickness of the specimen shown in Figure 2 is 6 mm and the ground truth material model is the 3D Hill48 yield criterion along with the p-model [6,7] to describe strain hardening, see Section 2.1 for more details.

Fig. 3. The DVT for two stereo-DIC systems observing the front and side of the used specimen. The strain component ϵ_{yy} in the tensile direction is shown for (a) Projected front surface (b) projected side surface.

2 Multi-sDIC and FEMU

In essence, a FEMU approach minimizes the discrepancy between a numerically computed and an experimentally acquired response by tuning the material behavior. Given that we use DIC, the response is the strain field in the AOI (front and side). However, in this paper the full-field displacement data of the front and the side surface is fed to the FEMU code. The correlation process in MatchID 3D was conducted using default settings, both front and side data were processed with a subset size of 21 px and a step size of 4 px. Hence, the first step in the identification process is to derive the strain fields from the experimentally acquired displacement fields. This is done using the strain window method [8] and the results are shown (strain window 7×7 DIC data points) in Figure 4. It can be inferred that i) inhomogeneous strain fields are generated, ii) the strain levels are sufficiently large to identify plastic material behavior and iii) all relevant strain components are activated. These strain fields are compared with the numerically computed strain fields of the FE model. An important caveat, however, is that the numerical strain fields are also computed via the strain window method (using the same strain window size as used for processing the experimental displacement data). To this end, the nodal displacements of the FE model are used to derive the strain tensor in the DIC data point. This approach mitigates the bias that is associated with different

strain calculation methods used in DIC and FEA. Prior to starting the inverse identification, it is of crucial importance to establish a relation between the DIC and the FEA coordinate system. Besides the displacement fields, also the experimental tensile force is provided to the FEMU platform. As such, the cost function consists of three parts, i.e. strains at the front surface, strains at the side surface and the experimental tensile force, more details on the cost function formulation can be found in [2].

Fig. 4. Reconstruction of the experimental strain field using the strain window method. Left column: side surface. Right column: front surface. All strain components are shown.

2.1 Material model

The reference material used to create the DVT corresponds with the 3D Hill48 yield criterion inversely calibrated for a 10 mm thick S690QL steel using the double perforated specimen shown in Figure 1. The 3D Hill48 yield criterion reads as:

$$\sigma_{eq}^2 = F(\sigma_{22} - \sigma_{33})^2 + G(\sigma_{33} - \sigma_{11})^2 + H(\sigma_{11} - \sigma_{22})^2 + 2L\sigma_{23}^2 + 2M\sigma_{31}^2 + 2N\sigma_{12}^2 \quad (1)$$

During the non-conventional tensile experiment, the tensile direction was aligned with the 45D [2]. The reference anisotropy parameters can be found in Table 1. The post-necking strain hardening behavior was modelled using the p-model [7] of which the parameters were inversely calibrated using a perforated tensile specimen in the RD [2]. The p-model reads as:

$$\sigma_{eq} = \begin{cases} K(\varepsilon_0 + \varepsilon_{eq}^{pl})^n & \text{if } \varepsilon_{eq}^{pl} \leq \varepsilon_{max} \\ K(\varepsilon_0 + \varepsilon_{max})^n + Q[1 - e^{-p(\varepsilon_{eq}^{pl} - \varepsilon_{max})}] & \text{if } \varepsilon_{eq}^{pl} > \varepsilon_{max} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

Table 1. Reference anisotropy parameters (3D Hill48) used in the DVT.

F	G	H	N	M	L
0.4879	0.470	0.530	1.412	1.877	1.259

2.2 Results and discussion

Figure 5 shows the identified anisotropy parameters as a function of the identification process, i.e the number of iterations. The dashed black lines represent the reference anisotropy parameters (Table 1). It can be seen that the initial guess of the material behavior corresponds to isotropic material behavior. After four iterations, convergence is obtained. It can be inferred that the in-plane anisotropy parameters (F , H and N) are accurately identified (relative error smaller than 1%). The shear anisotropy parameters (M and L) exhibit a relative error of about 5%. The identification of the out-of-plane shear anisotropy parameters is clearly less accurate than the identification accuracy of the in-plane anisotropy parameters. This could not be revealed without the use of the DVT. Indeed, the verification experiments shown in Figure 2 predict a perfect identification quality. By accounting for the complete measurement chain, it becomes clear that the results shown in Figure 2 merely verify the FEMU implementation. This shows the importance of accounting for the metrological DIC aspects in the DVT. Indeed, the FEDEF module enables to create a realistic digital virtual twin of the experiment. As opposed the results shown in Fig. 2, it is shown in Fig. 5 that the metrological aspects of DIC need to be considered in assessing the identification quality of the adopted FEMU approach. From an engineering perspective, the identification quality of M and L is still acceptable, as 5% is often considered to be feasible for engineering applications [9]. Yet, it clearly shows that the proposed inverse method can be improved. The DVT can for example be used to study the most optimal DIC settings to capture the out-of-plane shear strains, or improve the specimen design so that less strong strain gradients are generated through the thickness. Moreover, the numerical optimization approach can also be improved with the aid of the DVT, by e.g. adding zero weight to small strains.

Fig. 5. Inversely identified anisotropy parameters based on the DVT: (a) N, M, L; (b) F, H.

3 Experimental validation

The results presented in the previous section fully rely on the DVT that predicted an inverse identification accuracy of 5%. In this section, we experimentally validate the inverse methodology to identify the 3D Hill 48 anisotropic yield criterion for a 12mm thick S700MC steel. Fig. 6 shows the experimental multi-sDIC set up. It can be inferred that the initial design (Fig. 2) is slightly modified to enable the measurement of the side surface. Table 1 (see Appendix) outlines the optimal DIC settings for the front and side surface. The specimen is mounted in a universal tensile machine with a load capacity of 250 kN. A random speckle pattern was applied to the test specimen. The crosshead speed of the tensile machine was 1 mm/min ensuring quasi-static test conditions. Synchronized images were captured with a frequency of 2 Hz. At a tensile force of 100,732 kN, we observed the desired thinning of the specimen through the thickness, which is crucial to activate the out-of-plane shear anisotropy parameters. This load step corresponds to a maximum equivalent von Mises strain of 0.45 and 0.64 for the front and side surface, respectively. Given that the maximum uniform tensile strain of the material is about 0.10, the post-necking hardening is modeled via the p-model [7]. The pre-necking part of the p-model was calibrated via a standard tensile test in the RD. The post-necking hardening parameter p for S700MC (12 mm) has been calibrated in a previous study [7]. The hardening parameters used in this section are reported in Table 2. The FE model of the experiment was built using Abaqus/Standard and meshed using C3D8R elements. The tensile direction was aligned with Diagonal Direction (DD) with respect to the RD. The simulation was force-driven with a maximum tensile load of 100,732 kN. The obtained displacement fields (front and side) were fed to our FEMU platform to identify the anisotropy parameters.

Fig. 6. Multi-sDIC setup: two stereo DIC systems are used to capture the front and side surface.

Table 2. Hardening parameters (p-model) of S700MC (12 mm).

Parameters	K	ε_0	n	p	ε_{\max}
values	1280.7	0.02936	0.168	3.49	0.10

3.1 Results and discussion

Fig. 7 shows the inversely identified anisotropy parameters as a function of the iterations during the FEMU process. The dashed lines represent the anisotropy parameters determined through the Lankford coefficients measured through standard tensile tests in the RD, DD and TD. It can be inferred from Fig. 7(a) that the inversely identified shear anisotropy parameter N corresponds to the one determined via the Lankford coefficients. In addition, Fig. 7(b) shows that the inversely identified in-plane anisotropy parameters have the same order of magnitude (within 10% error) than the ones determined via the Lankford coefficients, yet clearly differ. The out-of-plane shear anisotropy parameters (M and L) cannot be compared with a reference value. In this regard, it can only be observed that convergence leads to anisotropic values. The inversely identified plastic anisotropy can be used to compare the experimental and the numerical strain fields. Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 show the comparison for the front and side surface, respectively. It can be seen that the experimental and numerical strain fields are in good agreement. The observed discrepancy with the Lankford ratios is not surprising given the limited predictive accuracy of the Hill48 yield function. In this regard, it must be noted that during the information rich tensile test, the material is probed under different stress states than in the standard tensile test used to determine the Lankford coefficients. The FEMU considers the strain fields and the global tensile force (and thus the stresses), while the Lankford ratios only consider the strain fields.

Fig. 7. Inversely identified anisotropy parameters. The dashed lines are the parameters identified through Lankford ratio.

4 Conclusions

This paper deals with the verification and experimental validation of a procedure to inversely identify the 3D plastic anisotropy of thick high strength steels. It is shown that an advanced Digital Virtual Twin (DVT) of the experiment enables to thoroughly verify and improve the inverse identification strategy. Based on a finite element simulation of the experiment, the complete measurement and identification strategy can be investigated. The DVT enables to predict the inverse identification accuracy when feeding the FEMU platform with full field displacement data. It is shown that the concept of the DVT, including the metrological aspects of DIC, is crucial to assess identification quality of a FEMU approach targeting 3D plastic anisotropy. The developed platform enables to further optimize the inverse identification procedure (experimentally as well as numerically). Finally, physical experiments on thick S700MC high strength steels were conducted to validate the proposed inverse identification strategy. It is shown that it is possible to simultaneously identify all sought anisotropy parameters from the proposed non-conventional tensile test.

Fig. 8. Front surface: plots of the experimentally measured strain fields (second column), numerically computed (third column) (using the identified anisotropy parameters), the discrepancy between the experimental and numerical strain fields (fourth column) and the absolute error between both.

Fig. 9. Side surface: plots of the experimentally measured strain fields (second column), numerically computed (third column) (using the identified anisotropy parameters), the discrepancy between the experimental and numerical strain fields (fourth column) and the absolute error between both..

Acknowledgements

This research was supported by the Research Fund for Coal and Steel under grant agreement No 888153. SC acknowledges Dr. Pascal Lava for the use of the MatchID software.

References

1. Denys K, Coppieters S, Seefeldt M, Debruyne D (2016) Multi-DIC setup for the identification of a 3D anisotropic yield surface of thick high strength steel using a double perforated specimen. *Mechanics of Materials*, 100, 96-108.
2. Denys K (2017) Investigation into the plastic material behaviour up to fracture of thick HSS using multi-DIC and FEMU. PhD Thesis, KU Leuven, Belgium.
3. Zhang Y, Van Bael A, Andrade-Campos A, Coppieters S (2022) Parameter identifiability analysis: Mitigating the non-uniqueness issue in the inverse identification of an anisotropic yield function. *International journal of solids and Structures* 243 111543.
4. Zhang Y, Gothivarekar S, Conde M, Van de Velde A, Paermentier B, Andrade-Campos A, Coppieters S, (2021) Enhancing the information-richness of sheet metal specimens for inverse identification of plastic anisotropy through strain fields. *International Journal of Mechanical Sciences* 214 10689.

5. Lava P, Cooreman S, Coppieters S, De Strycker M, Debruyne D (2009). Assessment of measuring errors in DIC using deformation fields generated by plastic FEA. *Optics and lasers in engineering*, 47 (7), 747-753.
6. Coppieters S, Kuwabara T (2014). Identification of Post-Necking Hardening Phenomena in Ductile Sheet Metal. *Experimental Mechanics*, (54), 1355-1371.
7. Final report European Research Project DURAMECH: Towards Best Practice for Bolted Connections in High Strength Steels. Project number 709962 (2016).
8. Sutton M, Orteu J-J, Schreier H (2009) *Image Correlation for Shape, Motion and Deformation Measurements. Basic Concepts, Theory and Applications*, Springer New York, NY.
9. Salehghaffari S, Rais-Rohani M, Marin EB, Bammann DJ, A new approach for determination of material constants of internal state variable based plasticity models and their uncertainty quantification, *Computational Materials Science*, Volume 55, 2012.

Appendix

Table 1. DIC setting after performance analysis for the front surface and the side surface of the non-conventional tensile test.

Surface	Front surface	Side surface
Processing parameters	Specification/Value	Specification/Value
Matching Criteria	ZNSSD	ZNSSD
Shape function	Quadratic	Quadratic
Interpolation function	Local Bicubic splines	Bicubic splines
Progress history	Spatial + update reference	Spatial + update reference
Subset size SS [px]	23	27
Step size(ST) [px]	2	2
Strain Window(SW)	15	15
Strain tensor-Polynomial	Eluer-Almansi-Q4	Eluer-Almansi-Q4
Virtual Stain Gauge(VSG) [px]	51	55
Pixel to mm	0.06940	0.05217
Noise level [%]	0.4658	0.3423
Displacement noise-floor [μm]	1.226 μm	1.580 μm
Strain noise-floor [-]	4.443×10^{-4}	4.979×10^{-4}